

Career talk: Panagiota Fatourou

What drives researchers to undertake an academic career in computer science? Here Panagiota Fatourou, a professor in the Department of Computer Science of the University of Crete, Greece and the Institute of Computer Science (ICS) of the Foundation for Research and Technology - Hellas (FORTH), shares her experience.

Published in HiPEAC futures column, HiPEAC info issue 70, <https://www.hipeac.net/magazine/7166.pdf>

What first sparked your interest in computer science?

When I was finishing high school, computer science was emerging as the science of the future. The more I came into touch with it, the more I realized that it would end up being one of the most influential sciences. Computer science has the power not only to determine future technology, but also to tremendously influence the evolution of many other fields, hopefully with a positive impact on the world. That was something that fascinated me.

When I started my undergraduate studies in computer science, computing technology was experiencing such a dynamic and rapid evolution that it was hard to follow all the technological advances. However, this also meant that there were countless opportunities for progression and learning. Amazingly, more than 25 years later, this is still true.

How did you come to specialize in distributed computing and in algorithms?

Parallel and distributed computing has a long history, dating back to the dawn of operating systems and networks. Although it has been studied for about the same time as computer science itself, the field is rapidly evolving and comes in many flavours, each with its own challenges to consider.

Some of the most pressing challenges are the performance and scalability issues that arise from the increased computing needs of modern applications. To meet these needs, we must exploit the full computational power of modern parallel and distributed platforms, whether in high-performance computing (HPC), in the cloud or at the edge.

This entails harnessing the power of dynamic, large-scale, heterogenous systems, for example by utilizing all their

computing elements – not only their multiple nodes, but also the multicore capabilities of each node, as well as the full capacity of the accelerators and devices attached. To do this, we have to utilize powerful mathematical methods and design novel algorithms to process large-scale, dynamic computations in a highly scalable and performance- or energy-efficient way. In the process, we have to find answers to fundamental questions that scientists in this field have been struggling to answer for decades.

By specializing in parallel and distributed computing, I had the chance to contribute to an exciting research field that has had significant impact on the evolution of computing in the past, and the potential for even greater impact in the future. My specialization in algorithms reflects my early passion for mathematics and for understanding the properties and limitations of the research problems I study. It also reflects my view that designing efficient algorithms will always be a challenging, intellectually demanding and intriguing task, thus rewarding to those who manage to tame it.

What should associations and projects like HiPEAC do to support computer scientists' careers?

Over the last few years, I have had plenty of opportunities to think about and work on these issues in the context of the Association for Computing Machinery (ACM), where I served as chair of the ACM Europe Council, as well as the founding director of the ACM Europe Research Visibility Working Group (RAISE). Our mission was to increase the visibility of European research and ensure a higher degree of recognition for the achievements of European researchers.

To do this, we proposed a series of actions:

- (i) highlight the role of Europe as a hub of research (for example by supporting the organization of more international events, including conferences);
- (ii) increase the number of European nominations for awards and distinctions (where these are genuinely deserved);
- (iii) increase awareness of the opportunities for recognition of the professional achievements of researchers (for example by identifying stakeholders, such as nominators and nominees, and educating European scholars about the opportunities available and how to take advantage of these);
- (iv) ensure geographical coverage in all events, committees, bodies, and activities of the association;
- (v) disseminate the achievements of European researchers (for example by publishing interviews, introducing awards, etc.).

The ACM Europe Council has adopted the above directions as part of its official goals and strategy, and is implementing actions along these directions. Even if only partially implemented, this action plan could have a significant impact on the career prospects of European computer scientists and truly boost the visibility of European research.

HiPEAC could play an important role here, for example by raising awareness about opportunities for researchers in Europe (awards, grants, etc.). This could be done by organizing appropriate dissemination activities, but also by instilling a culture among members of the community which is conducive to taking up this kind of opportunities. HiPEAC could also organize and promote targeted events; while the HiPEAC conference is a great initiative in this direction, there is room for other kinds of events. For instance, events bringing leading HiPEAC researchers together with researchers from other disciplines, to identify common ground for collaboration, and events specifically aimed at early career researchers.

Do you have any tips for researchers who are just starting out in their careers, in particular women?

Studying computer science provides excellent employment opportunities, a situation which is likely to continue given the predicted labour shortages in the future. Today, computing is woven into almost all of our activities, so it is a rewarding field of study.

In any case, I think it is important to start your career with passion. Believe in yourself and focus on your professional goals. Be courageous and fight for what you have dreamt of. Don't waste your energy trying to become what others expect you to be. Instead, focus on what inspired you to become a computer scientist. Be open to knowledge and to different professional experiences; be active and energetic; accept constructive criticism and learn how to push forward.

From a technical perspective, ensure that you have the necessary theoretical and algorithmic background to solve new, challenging problems, and that you know how to express yourself concisely. These are skills that have the power to pave the way to greater success.

Women in computer science work in environments that are heavily male dominated. Like others who are a minority in their field, they may experience professional bias. All kinds of people, irrespective of gender, race, age, disability, sexual orientation, etc., are equally needed in science and should have the same opportunities for professional success. We should get informed about societal stereotypes, which often follow people from childhood, and try to recognize and eliminate them.